

ENER GIZE

SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY
TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

Review of Regional Urban - Industrial Park (Energy Cooperation) Initiatives

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D2.1 - Review of Regional Urban - Industrial Park (Energy Cooperation) Initiatives

Authors:

Anja GAHLEITNER (ENERGIEINSTITUT AN DER JOHANNES KEPLER UNIVERSITÄT LINZ)

Melanie KNÖBL (ENERGIEINSTITUT AN DER JOHANNES KEPLER UNIVERSITÄT LINZ)

Sebastian GOERS (ENERGIEINSTITUT AN DER JOHANNES KEPLER UNIVERSITÄT LINZ)

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Authors	Anja GAHLEITNER (ENERGIEINSTITUT AN DER JOHANNES KEPLER UNIVERSITÄT LINZ), Melanie KNÖBL (ENERGIEINSTITUT AN DER JOHANNES KEPLER UNIVERSITÄT LINZ), Sebastian GOERS (ENERGIEINSTITUT AN DER JOHANNES KEPLER UNIVERSITÄT LINZ)
Contributors	Olga BARRACHINA (ESTRATS CONSULTORIA ESTRATEGICA), Segis VERDAGUER (ESTRATS CONSULTORIA ESTRATEGICA), Marta ARNIANI (THREE O'CLOCK), Marta CHÀFER (INSTITUT CATALA D'ENERGIA), Simon MOSER (ENERGIEINSTITUT AN DER JOHANNES KEPLER UNIVERSITÄT LINZ), Anna ARIAS (IRIS)

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Executive Summary

The ENERGIZE project, co-funded by the European Commission under the LIFE Clean Energy Transition program, aims to accelerate the clean energy transition in European industrial zones. ENERGIZE seeks to reduce CO₂ emissions, enhance energy efficiency, and create sustainable skills and job opportunities by fostering collaborative energy models.

This report, 'D2.1: Review of Regional Urban - Industrial Park (Energy Cooperation) Initiatives', explores the role of (urban) eco-industrial parks in achieving these objectives. It focuses on theoretical concepts, data collection, and best practices to inform the ENERGIZE's pilot initiatives. The selected best-practice examples can serve as a model for the ENERGIZE pilot regions. By adapting proven models to local conditions, ENERGIZE can replicate successes while addressing region-specific challenges. For example, regions with a strong production base or access to renewable energy sources can benefit from targeted industrial symbiosis processes.

Urban eco-industrial parks play a pivotal role in combining economic growth with sustainability. The discussed key concepts include:

- **Circular Economy:** A model that extends product lifecycles through reuse, repair, and recycling.
- **Industrial Ecology:** A multidisciplinary approach optimizing material and energy flows across industries.
- **Industrial Symbiosis:** Collaboration among industries to exchange by-products, energy, and resources.
- **Energy Cooperation:** Joint initiatives for energy generation, sharing, and efficiency among stakeholders.

The report focuses on the systematic data collection and analysis of 121 industrial park initiatives, including 110 in Europe and 15 from other global regions. Key parameters for assessing (urban eco-) industrial parks are defined; such as geographical scope, operational status, types of actors involved, and forms of collaboration. The data collection reveals that most parks are actively operational, demonstrating mature and scalable models for collaboration. The majority of the initiatives often involve diverse stakeholders, including industries, municipalities, SMEs, utility providers and research institutions. Common forms of collaboration include by-product exchange (waste-to-resource), resource recovery (recycling and reuse), and shared utility systems (energy and water). Several parks prioritize renewable energy integration and energy efficiency as core strategies.

Selected best-practice examples illustrate adaptable practices, such as surplus energy redistribution, waste minimization, and integration of renewable energy technologies. Key recommendations for ENERGIZE initiatives include leveraging location advantages, adopting industrial symbiosis and circular economy principles, and fostering stakeholder engagement to ensure project success and scalability. The integration of supportive policies and long-term planning further enhances the viability and sustainability of energy cooperation models.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CE	Circular Economy
CEC	Citizen energy Communities
CEP	Clean Energy Package for all Europeans
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
EC	Energy Cooperation
e.g.	For example
EIP	Eco-Industrial Park
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse gas
IEMD	International Electricity Market Directive
IPP	Industrial Park Platform
IS	Industrial symbiosis
IE	Industrial ecology
KIA	Kwiwana Industrial Area
KIC	Kwinana Industries Council
NIMBY	Not in my backyard
REC	Renewable energy communities
RECP	Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
REIP	Relvão Eco-Industrial Park
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
UNIDO	United Nations Industrial Development Organization

1 Introduction

The European Union has committed to achieving net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050. Within this framework, the ENERGIZE project aims to demonstrate cooperative energy models in industrial zones across Europe, including Catalonia, Italy, the Czech Republic, and Austria. The project seeks to reduce CO₂ emissions through initiatives like renewable energy generation, energy savings, and skills development in industrial parks, while also driving job creation and influencing policy. With support from over 20 industry players and associations, ENERGIZE is fostering industrial renewable energy communities. A digital hub will provide tools, training, and resources to scale these models globally, based on lessons learned from its pilot zones. ENERGIZE aims to showcase the potential for industrial collaboration to promote sustainable energy practices.

ENERGIZE's Work Package (WP) 2 'Operational Framework and analysis of energy cooperation landscape' conducts a detailed benchmarking of past and current initiatives related to energy efficiency, industrial communities, circularity, and industrial ecology. It also reviews legal and socio-economic requirements for business models. The goal is to identify existing achievements, draw lessons from other experiences, and pinpoint areas for improvement. The outcome will be a comprehensive assessment of the technical, legal, and socio-economic requirements needed to establish successfully urban eco-industrial energy communities.

Within this WP, Task 2.1 focuses on gathering and reviewing existing and past initiatives related to (urban) eco-industrial parks, with a specific emphasis on the participation, collaboration and energy cooperation between businesses within these parks and their surrounding areas. The aim is to analyse how such initiatives have facilitated collaboration, energy sharing, or other forms of cooperative engagement among industrial entities and their neighbouring communities on European and global scale. This review provides valuable insights into best practices and potential opportunities for enhancing energy efficiency and (renewable) energy cooperation in similar settings for ENERGIZE.

The outcomes of Task 2.1 are presented in this deliverable. It includes an introductory overview of the theory and concepts of (urban eco-) industrial parks, industrial symbiosis, industrial ecology, circularity and energy cooperation in Section 2. In Section 3, key parameters are defined, which allow the collection of concrete initiatives providing a comprehensive overview of (urban eco-) industrial park initiatives. The data collection is also available in the accompanying Excel file *Data Collection D.2.1* with detailed information on the analysed industry park initiatives. Further, the collected data and information are analysed. In Section 4, key findings are derived.

2 (Urban eco-) Industrial parks: theoretical outline and concepts

In this section, key features, theoretical outline and concepts of (urban eco-) industrial parks and their connection with each other are described based on findings in scientific literature and specific literature on industry parks and industrial symbiosis. These are subsequently used to provide an overview of (urban eco-) industrial parks and to identify, map and catalogue the initiatives in Section 3.

2.1 (Urban eco-) Industrial parks

Following the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), “[a]n industrial park is a tract of land developed and subdivided into plots according to a comprehensive plan with the provision of roads, transportation and public utilities, sometimes also with common facilities, for use by a group of manufacturers” [1]. Urban industrial parks aim to balance the needs of industrial growth with urban development, enhancing economic competitiveness while minimizing impacts on the surrounding urban environment [2]. These parks are specialized areas within cities designed to accommodate clusters of industrial activities and businesses. They are planned to integrate urban and industrial functions, providing space for manufacturing, logistics, and related services, while ensuring the availability of infrastructure such as transportation and utilities. These parks aim to stimulate economic growth, support job creation and attract investment by providing companies with access to resources and proximity to markets [2], [3]. A key feature of these parks is their ability to promote “urban-industrial integration”, which links industrial activity with urban development. This integration supports better planning for housing, transportation, and services for workers, and aims to reduce the disconnection between residential and industrial areas [2].

In recent years, there has been a trend towards the development of “eco-industrial parks” (EIP), which emphasize sustainability by focusing on resource efficiency, waste reduction, and environmental management. These parks are designed to foster symbiotic relationships between companies, allowing them to share resources and minimize environmental impact, creating a model for sustainable industrial growth [4], [5], [6], [7].

However, individual companies still face technical and financial barriers to replacing fossil fuels with renewable energy sources, which hinders the installation of renewable energy. The EIP concept therefore aims to create synergies between companies, enabling them to use natural and economic resources together and efficiently, while promoting the use of renewable energy sources in industry. Synergies between EIPs and adjacent urban areas can lead to the development of optimized energy production facilities, so that the surplus energy is available to meet part of the energy needs of the surrounding cities [4]. This concept of industrial and urban symbiosis is illustrated in Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1: Concepts of eco-industrial parks and urban-industrial symbiosis.

Sources: [4], [8].

2.2 Circularity

The Circular Economy (CE) is a sustainable economic model that aims to maximize the lifespan of products, materials and resources in the economy and minimize waste. Instead of following a linear “take-make-consume-dispose” approach, CE emphasizes strategies such as reuse, repair, refurbishment and recycling. This keeps raw materials in the economy throughout the entire life cycle of a product in order to optimize resource use and reduce waste [9].

This model contributes significantly to climate protection, biodiversity and the reduction of GHG. It also supports other key EU objectives, such as the green recovery, the energy savings plan and global sustainable development. In the EU, an action plan for CE was introduced in 2015, comprising 54 measures to put the EU on the path to a more sustainable economy. Key measures relate to waste management, reducing landfill and tackling food and plastic waste [10].

In 2020, the EU published another Circular Economy Action Plan as part of its Green Deal. This aims to make sustainable products the norm, promote the reduction of waste and accelerate the promotion of CE practices in resource-intensive sectors such as electronics, vehicles, textiles, construction and food. In addition, consumer rights are to be strengthened and companies are encouraged to make products more durable, repairable and sustainable [9].

A further important goal of CE is to reduce dependence on raw materials, particularly with regard to critical raw materials for future technologies such as batteries and electric motors. This strategy minimizes risks such as price fluctuations and the availability of raw materials, especially as many of these raw materials have to be imported from non-EU countries [10]. In addition, CE could create up to 700,000 new jobs in the EU by 2030, which would simultaneously increase competitiveness and stimulate innovation. Consumers will also benefit from more durable and efficient products that save costs in the long term [10]. Through the EU's various initiatives and measures, CE should help to create a carbon-neutral, environmentally friendly and fully circular economy by 2050 [11].

2.3 Industrial ecology

Industrial Ecology (IE) is a multidisciplinary field that focuses on understanding and optimizing the flow of materials, energy, and resources through industrial systems. It applies ecological principles - such as energy efficiency, recycling, and symbiosis (see Subsection 2.4) - to industrial processes in order to create more sustainable and environmentally friendly systems [12], [13], [14].

IE treats industrial activities as interconnected parts of larger systems. It considers the environmental impacts not only of individual factories or businesses but of entire supply chains and sectors. This holistic view helps in designing sustainable industrial systems that minimize environmental harm [15]. In practice, IE can be applied in settings like EIPs, where sectors like manufacturing, energy, and agriculture collaborate to share resources and optimize waste management. The concept of 'waste-as-a-resource', known as 'industrial symbiosis' (see Subsection 2.4), promotes the use of by-products and minimizes overall waste. IE is closely related to the CE model [16] where the aim is to keep products, materials, and resources in use for as long as possible. Instead of the traditional linear model of 'take, make, waste', it promotes recycling, reusing, and remanufacturing.

2.4 Industrial symbiosis

Industrial Symbiosis (IS) is a systemic approach to resource efficiency, where multiple industries collaborate to exchange materials, energy, water, or by-products with the aim of minimizing waste and optimizing the use of resources. Through such exchanges, companies can transform waste or underutilized resources from one production process into valuable inputs for another, reducing environmental impact and operational costs. This practice supports CE objectives (see Subsection 2.2) and contributes to sustainable development by promoting innovation and resource conservation, which are key elements of the EU's Green Deal and CE strategies [17].

IS fosters integrated industrial systems where symbiotic relationships reduce waste, energy consumption, and raw material use. The benefits extend beyond environmental sustainability to include economic gains

and enhanced industrial resilience [18]. This collaborative model is actively promoted by the European Union through initiatives such as the Green Deal Industrial Plan, which aims to create a more sustainable and competitive industrial ecosystem across Europe by scaling up clean technology industries [17].

Moreover, IS plays a key role in the EU Green Deal by optimizing resource use and reducing waste through industrial cooperation, helping align industries with CE goals [18]. Programs like RECP Clubs and industrial waste mapping help industries implement symbiotic practices, driving both environmental and economic benefits [19]. Tools such as the Industrial Symbiosis Toolkit offer guidelines for industries to collaborate effectively, optimize resource use, and reduce environmental footprints [20].

2.5 Energy cooperation

Energy cooperation refers to a collaborative approach to a sustainable energy solution, such as energy production, procurement and consumption among different stakeholders with the purpose to create opportunities for optimized energy demand and improved sustainability. Such cooperation can take various forms, including partnerships within industrial parks, between industrial companies and surrounding communities. By pooling sources, more efficient energy solutions can be implemented, such as shared energy production plants, district heating systems, and the reuse of waste heat [21].

Energy cooperation is closely linked to the concept of Industrial Symbiosis. Both IS and Energy Cooperation involve collaboration between different entities. IS focuses on the development and implementation of resource exchange between companies and therefore also includes energy cooperation [22]. **These concepts should be seen as complementary, working together in synergy to maximize resource efficiency and sustainability.**

Energy cooperation is not explicitly defined or targeted within European energy policies, but fits well within the broader sustainability goals of the European Union, as the EU has committed itself to IS in its "Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe." Moser S. and V. Rodin stated that energy cooperation is an integral part of IS. It focuses specifically on energy-related activities and can include participants from either the same or different sectors, typically located in close geographic proximity. Other institutions may also be involved in such collaborations. Energy cooperation often entails knowledge sharing, joint procurement and service provision, as well as the physical exchange of energy and/or the production of renewable energy [23]. Trust and security are very important for energy cooperations, robust communication and coordination are therefore essential for the success of such collaborations [22]. By collaborating on energy-related activities, stakeholders can optimize resource use, improve energy efficiency, and create shared value, contributing to both environmental and financial gains [24].

Still energy cooperation remains relatively rare. One key challenge lies in the heterogeneity of different energy cooperation projects, which makes it difficult to generalize or apply a one-size-fits-all approach. Each partnership has its own unique characteristics, including the energy needs of the involved companies, the local infrastructure, and the level of trust between stakeholders [21].

Energy cooperation is a powerful instrument for enhancing energy efficiency and sustainability. By overcoming the barriers and building trust it can play a significant role in the clean energy transition [21].

The terms *energy cooperation* and *energy community* are often used synonymously. The concepts of energy cooperation and energy community both relate to collective efforts. However, in this context, we

aim to distinguish between them. While there is no formal legal framework for wider energy cooperation, energy communities are supported by specific regulations which are discussed in the following Subsections 2.5.1 and 2.5.2.

2.5.1 EU Legal Framework of Renewable Energy Communities & Citizen Energy Communities

In 2019, the European Union presented a comprehensive update of its energy policy framework to enable a sustainable energy transition. This new framework is known as the Clean Energy Package for all Europeans (CEP).

The most important documents within the CEP for energy communities are the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) and the International Electricity Market Directive (IEMD), which contain regulations and definitions for Renewable Energy Communities (REC)s and Citizens' Energy Communities (CEC) [25].

The Directive (EU) 2019/944 (IEMD), Article 2 (11) defines a CEC as follows:

“a legal entity that:

- a) is based on voluntary and open participation and is effectively controlled by members or shareholders that are natural persons, local authorities, including municipalities, or small enterprises;*
- b) has for its primary purpose to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits to its members or shareholders or to the local areas where it operates rather than to generate financial profits; and*
- c) may engage in generation, including from renewable sources, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, energy efficiency services or charging services for electric vehicles or provide other energy services to its members or shareholders.”*

Art. 16 clarifies the regulatory framework which the Member States need to provide [26].

The Directive 2018/2001 (RED II) Article 2 (16) defines a REC as follows:

“a legal entity:

- a) which, in accordance with the applicable national law, is based on open and voluntary participation, is autonomous, and is effectively controlled by shareholders or members that are located in the proximity of the renewable energy projects that are owned and developed by that legal entity;*
- b) the shareholders or members of which are natural persons, SMEs or local authorities, including municipalities;*
- c) the primary purpose of which is to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits for its shareholders or members or for the local areas where it operates, rather than financial profits”.*

Art. 22 clarifies the regulatory framework which the Member States need to provide [27].

2.5.2 Definition of Renewable Energy Communities & Citizen Energy Communities

Renewable Energy Communities and Citizen Energy Communities (CEC) share a common purpose - they both enable collective action to support the clean energy transition. The collective action can be to produce, distribute, manage, supply, consume and aggregate the own energy. They are both legal entities and are characterised by open participation, voluntarism, control and ownership by citizens, local

authorities and smaller enterprises, and a focus on social and environmental benefits rather than financial profit. [28, p. 7]. As displayed in Table 2-1, the two types of energy communities can be distinguished [28, p. 8].

Table 2-1: Difference between the two types of Energy Communities.

Source: [28, p. 8]

	Renewable energy communities (REC)	Citizen energy communities (CEC)
<i>Geographical scope</i>	Limited geographical scope, proximity of the REC	No limitation on geographical scope between production and consumption
<i>Operation</i>	Renewable energy-based heating and electricity	Electricity
<i>Participants</i>	SMEs, local authorities and natural persons; precondition: no member or stakeholders act in the energy sector and have decision-making power	Natural persons, local authorities and micro, small and medium-sized enterprises
<i>Autonomy</i>	Needs to be autonomous	Not necessary
<i>Effective control</i>	Can be controlled by SMEs	Exclude medium and large enterprises

2.6 Conclusion

The concepts presented above demonstrate that urban EIPs exhibit facets of industrial ecology, circular economy, and industrial symbiosis, and are generally compatible with the concept of energy cooperation. In summary, the following conclusion can be drawn:

Urban eco-industrial parks can act as platforms for implementing **industrial ecology** by facilitating **industrial symbiosis** and promoting **energy cooperation**, which together contribute to achieving **circularity** and are integrated into urban settings.

Through collaboration and resource sharing, businesses in these parks can reduce waste, optimize resource use, and improve energy efficiency, aligning with the principles of a circular economy. These interconnections foster more sustainable, resilient, and economically efficient (industrial) environments and balance the needs of industrial growth with urban development.

Figure 2-2: Urban eco-industrial parks in the context of industrial ecology, industrial symbiosis, energy cooperations and circularity.

Source: Own compilation.

3 Data collection, overview and best-practices

Building on the theoretical foundations derived in Section 2, this section collects data and information to provide an overview of the practical characteristics of EIPs. Key parameters for analysis are defined in Subsection 3.1, followed by a presentation of the data collection results in Subsection 3.2. Complementing the textual descriptions, detailed information for each identified initiative is included in the associated Excel file *Data Collection D.2.1* for this deliverable. This file also contains additional data on ‘Integrated regulatory frameworks’, ‘Incentives, financial support mechanisms, strategies, tax measures’, and ‘Social factors’, which are relevant to other tasks within this work package.

The attached Excel file *Data Collection D.2.1* was created to systematically collect, organize, and analyze data on (urban eco-) industrial parks from Europe and around the world. Its primary purpose is to provide a comprehensive knowledge base that supports the ENERGIZE project by offering detailed insights into the operational status, collaboration models, resource-sharing practices, and the other key parameters of existing initiatives. It compiles data from diverse sources, ensuring that all relevant information is consolidated in one accessible format. By standardizing parameters such as geographical scope, size, forms of IS, and actors involved, the file enables the systematic comparison of different initiatives. The dataset helps identify successful strategies and challenges in implementing IS, which are essential for deriving actionable recommendations for ENERGIZE.

ENERGIZE SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES		(Urban eco-) Industrial Park Initiatives (incl. information on energy cooperation)						
Initiative	Country	Geographical Scope	Operational Status	Size	Type of Actors Involved/Participants	Industry Focus	Number of Involved Companies	Forms of Industrial Symbiosis
Ferrara Industrial Area	Italy	of Park on the shores of the Po River	Active/Operational	32,000 ha	European Industrial Council	Aluminum refinery, metal	7-100	Water, steam, waste
Toronto Park	Canada	Midland, New Toronto	Active/Operational	2,300 ha	Government, industry, academia	Food processing, printing, office	1,000	Water, steam, waste
Hubei Province Economic Development Zone	China	the middle north part of the province	Active/Operational	380,000 ha	Industrial firms	Chemical, textile, cement & construction	100	Water, steam, waste
Integrated Biosystem Monitor for Bays Town	Spain	Bay of Biscaya	Active/Operational	n/a ha	Agribusiness and industry	Food processing, pharmaceuticals, chemicals	100	Water, steam, waste
Tema	Ghana	Port of Tema	Active/Operational	94,425 ha	Government, industry, academia	Manufacturing, services	100	Water, steam, waste
Pharmaceutical Cluster, Guatemala	Guatemala	Guatemala	Active/Operational	n/a ha	Government, industry, academia	Pharmaceuticals	100	Water, steam, waste
Suncheon and Ocheon Industrial Park	South Korea	Urban metropolitan city	Active/Operational	6,340 ha	Government, industry, academia	Manufacturing, services	100	Water, steam, waste
Riverside Eco-Park	USA	Massachusetts	Active/Operational	0.1 ha	Government, industry, academia	Manufacturing, services	100	Water, steam, waste
Eco-industrial park of Drenth	USA	Massachusetts	Active/Operational	n/a ha	Government, industry, academia	Manufacturing, services	100	Water, steam, waste
Landmark Eco-Industrial Park	USA	Massachusetts	Active/Operational	40.47 ha	Government, industry, academia	Manufacturing, services	100	Water, steam, waste
Hui Sheng Industrial Zone	China	Guangdong	Active/Operational	304 ha	Government, industry, academia	Manufacturing, services	100	Water, steam, waste
ADAP Green Industrial Park	India	Telangana	Active/Operational	80 ha	Government, industry, academia	Manufacturing, services	100	Water, steam, waste
Varanasi Industrial Park	India	Uttar Pradesh	Active/Operational	527 ha	Government, industry, academia	Manufacturing, services	100	Water, steam, waste

Figure 3-1: Image excerpt from the Excel file created on (urban eco-) industrial park initiatives worldwide (part of D2.1).

Source: Own compilation.

Finally, Subsection 3.3 highlights selected best-practice examples of (urban) EIPs in Europe and worldwide that may hold relevance for the ENERGIZE project.

3.1 Key parameters for data collection

Key parameters were selected as part of the data search for (urban eco-) industrial park initiatives on EU and global scale. Providing strong criteria for grouping, consistency and ensuring a clear focus, these parameters - displayed in Table 3-1 - are essential for the overview and the results in Subsection 3.2.

Table 3-1: Key parameters for data collection on (urban eco-) industrial parks.

Key parameter	Definition
<i>Geographical scope</i>	<i>Geographical scope</i> refers to the specific physical area or region that is covered by the industrial park.
<i>Operational status</i>	<i>Operational status</i> refers to the current condition or functioning state of a selected industrial park. It tracks the parks' availability, performance, and readiness by indicating whether the industrial park is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active/Operational: Fully functioning and capable of operating - Planned: Operations are planned for the future
<i>Size</i>	<i>Size</i> refers to the physical magnitude of the park and is expressed in ha.
<i>Type of actors involved/participants</i>	<i>Type of actors involved/participants</i> refers to the different entities that participate in the selected industrial park. Key types of actors / participants are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industrial firms - Municipalities - Utility providers - Research institutions - Policy makers - SMEs and start-ups
<i>Forms of industrial symbiosis, industrial ecology, energy cooperations and circularity</i>	<i>Forms of industrial symbiosis, industrial ecology, energy cooperation and circularity</i> refer to the different ways in which companies or industries collaborate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By-product Exchange (Waste-to-Resource) - Utility Sharing (Energy, Water, Infrastructure) - Energy Cascading (Heat Integration) - Resource Recovery (Recycling & Reuse Networks) - Collaborative Logistics & Services

<i>Optional / if available</i>	
<i>Cooperation drivers</i>	<p><i>Cooperation drivers</i> refer to the factors or motivations that encourage the participants and actors to collaborate. These drivers can vary depending on the context but generally include a mix of economic, social, strategic, or environmental incentives that make cooperation appealing or necessary:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost savings - Access to resources - Risk reduction - Regulatory compliance
<i>Integrated regulatory framework</i>	<p><i>Integrated regulatory framework</i> is about whether there exists a structured system of policies, laws, guidelines, and best practices that govern the establishment, operation, and management of the industrial parks.</p>
<i>Incentives, financial support and strategies, and tax measures</i>	<p><i>Incentives, financial support, strategies, and tax measures</i> refer to various tools and policies used to encourage desired developments (e.g. economic growth, innovation, sustainability, or compliance with regulations) with the industrial park initiatives.</p>
<i>Social factors</i>	<p><i>Social factors</i> can be critical in determining the success or failure of new (large-scale) industrial initiatives. Balancing community concerns with project goals is key to achieving social acceptance. Some important social factors include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acceptance - NIMBY ("Not In My Back Yard") - Community engagement - Perceived benefits and risks - Cultural and ethical values

Source: Own compilation under consideration of [7], [15], [29], [30].

3.2 Results and overview

A total of 125 industry parks were analyzed as part of the data collection, considering the theoretical outline discussed in Section 2 and the key parameters defined in Subsection 3.1. The focus was on initiatives from Europe, with data collected on 110 initiatives from various countries. The data collection for the non-European level comprises 15 examples.

It should be noted that the data collection does not claim to be comprehensive due to the large number and variety of initiatives. As can be seen in the scientific literature [31], [32] and in reports by [1], [7], a large number of EIPs exist and their concept is being increasingly observed and implemented worldwide.

The data and information were collected and prepared through desk research. This process primarily relied on peer-reviewed publications focused on 'eco-industrial parks' and 'industrial symbiosis'. Additionally, reports and databases from international organizations such as the World Bank and UNIDO ([1], [7], [15]) as well as publicly accessible online sources, were utilized.

3.2.1 Collected data and results for the European level

For the European level, 110 examples were identified. As can be seen in the Excel file *Data Collection D.2.1*, the data search and processing yielded country-specific results. Most initiatives were identified for Norway (9), Spain (8), Austria, Finland, France, Italy and the Netherlands (6 each) .

The data collection, encompassing examples from various countries, highlights a wide range in the sizes of industrial parks. These differences can be attributed to the diverse forms of collaboration among participants from various industries and sectors, as well as variations in the industrial, economic, and demographic structures of different countries or regions.

Regarding the maturity status of the initiatives analyzed, most are in active operation. Of the 95 industrial parks where the status could be determined, the majority are operational, while only 5% remain in the planning phase. Participants in these initiatives include companies from one or more industries, as commonly seen in traditional industrial parks, alongside municipalities, utility providers, policymakers, SMEs, and start-ups. Furthermore, research institutions and universities are actively involved in some of these initiatives. A wide array of industries is represented, particularly those from the chemical sector, material goods production, the food industry, and (renewable) energy production.

The initiatives implement various forms of IS, with the most prevalent approaches being by-product exchange (waste-to-resource), resource recovery (recycling and reuse networks), and utility sharing (energy, water, and infrastructure). Renewable energy utilization and energy efficiency are frequently emphasized across numerous examples. The connection to the urban environment is not specifically implemented in the evaluated examples or the 'urban part' is not yet integrated into the symbiosis concept, but detailed information can be found in the best-practice examples (see Subsection 3.3) and in the Excel file *Data Collection D.2.1*.

Table 3-2: Overview on collected European EIP initiatives.

Source: Own compilation.

Parameters	
# Analysed initiatives	110
Operational status	Mostly running (95%)
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industry (mostly manufacturing, chemical, food) - Municipalities - SMEs - Energy utilities
Leading forms of industrial symbiosis	Waste-to-resource, resource recovery, utility sharing (including renewable energy utilization and fulfilling energy efficiency)

3.2.2 Collected data and results for the non-European level

The initiatives identified originate from Asia (8), North America (5), and Australia (2). It is important to note, as with the data collection for Europe, that the compilation is not exhaustive.

Similar to the analysis of European initiatives, there is significant variation in the sizes of the industrial parks. Regarding their operational status, all parks for which status information was available are fully operational. Participants span various industries, including manufacturing and the chemical sector, with heavy industry frequently represented. The primary forms of industrial symbiosis (IS) identified are associated with by-product exchange (waste-to-resource). However, detailed information specifically addressing urban-industrial symbiosis was limited. For further insights, refer to the selected best-practice examples in Subsection 3.3.

Table 3-3: Overview on collected non-European EIP initiatives.

Source: Own compilation.

Parameters	
# Analysed initiatives	15
Operational status	Running
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industry (mostly iron/steel, manufacturing, chemical, food) - Municipalities
Leading form of industrial symbiosis	Waste-to-resource

3.3 Selected best-practice examples of (urban eco-) industrial parks

The concept of EIPs has gained increasing attention in recent years, as highlighted by numerous case studies published in scientific literature [4], [6], [30], [33]. These studies show that these initiatives are taking place globally, with Kalundborg in Denmark and Ulsan in South Korea frequently cited as prominent examples (see **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**). Our report includes seven of recognized examples of EIPs worldwide in addition to the detailed data collection in the attached Excel file Data Collection D.2.1 and the overview in Subsections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2. These parks are:

- Kanaalkant (Belgium) – *Subsection 0*
- Kalundborg (Denmark) – *Subsection 3.3.2*
- Relvão (Portugal) – *Subsection 3.3.3*
- Händelö (Sweden) – *Subsection 3.3.4*
- Kwinana (Australia) – *Subsection 3.3.5*
- Kawasaki (Japan) – *Subsection 3.3.6*
- Ulsan (South Korea) – *Subsection 3.3.7*

The selected best-practice examples were chosen because they are among the most frequently cited cases in the literature and have demonstrated significant success in implementing key aspects of (urban) eco-Industrial Parks. These examples showcase how industry can be effectively integrated with urban environments, promoting resource efficiency, circular economy principles, and sustainable development. Each case highlights specific factors such as strong stakeholder collaboration, innovative resource-sharing models, and long-term sustainability efforts that make them exemplary models for future urban-industrial cooperation. The following table provides an overview of the selected EIPs and the aspects that make them relevant as best-practice examples. Table 3-5: Description of the indicators for selection as best-practices.

Table 3-4: Highlighting the selected best-practices in reports and scientific literature.

Source: Own compilation.

Author	Title	Year	Results for ...							Link	
			Kanaalkant	Kalundborg	Relvão	Händelö	Kwinana	Kawasaki	Ulsan		
EU4Environment	Eco-Industrial Parks Advancement Guide	2024		X						1	
NCPC	Eco-Industrial Parks International best practice examples	2024		X				X		2	
APEC Policy Partnership for Science, Technology and Innovation	World-Class Circular Economy Industrial Parks: Best Practices, Challenges, Opportunities, Training and Collaboration	2024							X	X	3
Federal Office for the Environment FOEN	International survey on eco-innovation parks	2014	X			X	X			X	4
Y. Sun et al.	Twelve pathways of carbon neutrality for industrial parks	2024		X					X	X	5
Franck Aggeri	Industrial eco-parks as drivers of the circular economy	2021		X						X	6
V. Rodin and S. Moser	From theory to practice: Supporting industrial decarbonization and energy cooperation in Austria	2022		X	X				X	X	7

Links:

- 1 <https://euneighbourseast.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/eco-industrial-park-guide.pdf>
- 2 https://www.industrialefficiency.co.za/eco-industrial-parks-international_best_practice/
- 3 https://www.apec.org/docs/default-source/publications/2024/3/224_ppsti_world-class-circular-economy-industrial-parks.pdf?sfvrsn=9e7d0042_2
- 4 <https://is4ie.org/resources/documents/5>
- 5 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.140753>
- 6 <https://journals.openedition.org/factsreports/6642>
- 7 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102863>

Table 3-5: Reasons for selection as best-practice.

Source: Own compilation.

Eco-Industrial Park	Why were they selected as best-practices?
Kanaalkant (Belgium)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proximity to Antwerp, enabling strong urban-industrial collaboration. - Shared infrastructure (waste heat, water treatment, logistics). - Effective application of circular economy principles (waste minimization, material loops).
Kalundborg (Denmark)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pioneer in industrial symbiosis, operating for decades. - Integration with urban infrastructure, especially district heating. - Strong cooperation between industries and city authorities, ensuring long-term sustainability.
Relvão (Portugal)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strategic location with proximity to urban centers. - Focus on circular economy and industrial symbiosis.
Händelö (Sweden)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Close cooperation with the city of Norrköping for district heating. - Utilization of renewable energy sources such as biogas from organic waste. - Strong circular economy strategies for waste minimization.
Kwinana (Australia)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positioned within a metropolitan area with access to ports. - Strong public-private partnerships enhancing sustainability efforts. - Government incentives promoting eco-friendly industrial practices.
Kawasaki (Japan)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Successful transformation from an industrialized area to a sustainable EIP. - Collaboration with city authorities to reduce environmental impact. - Implementation of advanced circular economy and industrial symbiosis strategies.
Ulsan (South Korea)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of green technology investments with urban energy systems. - Public-private cooperation for sustainable industrial development. - Strong focus on energy efficiency and industrial waste management.

3.3.1 Kanaalkant (Belgium)

Country:	Belgium
Geographical Scope:	Situated along the Albert Canal in Antwerp, a strategic location that enhances its role as a logistical and industrial hub.
Status:	Active industrial zone with ongoing redevelopment projects aimed at transforming it into a modern, circular industrial ecosystem.
Size:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approximately 400 hectares, it is one of the largest industrial zones in Flanders • The park hosts over 800 companies and employs more than 9,000 people
Number of members	<u>600 companies</u>
Legal entity	Municipalities of Wijnegem, Schoten, and Antwerp, as well as De Vlaamse Waterweg (The Flemish Waterway), the Province of Antwerp, and POM Antwerp (Provincial Development Agency).
Forms of Industrial Symbiosis:	<p><u>Resource Sharing:</u> Companies collaborate to exchange materials and by-products to optimize resource efficiency.</p> <p><u>Energy Cooperation:</u> Planned initiatives for shared heating and cooling systems aim to reduce energy consumption and carbon emissions.</p> <p><u>Waste Minimization:</u> Focus on circularity by treating waste as a resource and reducing overall waste streams.</p>
Relevance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared use of waste heat, water treatment, and logistics with Antwerp city. • Cooperation at local (Antwerp) and sub-local (Kanaalkant) levels, with trust and communication as key factors. • Focus on closing material loops and reducing waste through resource optimization. • Companies, municipalities, and utilities mutually benefit, enhancing viability. • Emphasis on resource sharing, particularly in energy and water management. • Continuous projects in sustainability and efficiency, supported by public and private investments.

Figure 3-2: Kanaalkant Eco-Industrial Park.

Source: [34].

The Kanaalkant Industrial Park exemplifies how strategic location, collaborative governance, and a commitment to sustainability can create a successful model for eco-industrial development. Located along the Albert Canal and near the Port of Antwerp, Kanaalkant benefits from unparalleled logistical advantages. These efficient transport networks facilitate resource distribution and waste management, making it a key hub for industries in the region.

Strong partnerships among government bodies, business associations, and local stakeholders have played a critical role in driving the park's transformation. The "kaderplan" serves as a comprehensive spatial and operational framework, ensuring coordinated redevelopment and sustainable growth.

A core strength of Kanaalkant lies in its dedication to the principles of CE. Through resource sharing, waste reduction, and energy efficiency initiatives, the park is revitalizing outdated infrastructure and positioning itself as a leader in sustainable industrial innovation. Ambitious projects underscore its role in advancing the transition to a more circular and efficient industrial ecosystem.

Why Kanaalkant Serves as an Exemplary Model

Kanaalkant Industrial Park showcases how eco-industrial principles can scale and adapt across diverse sectors and businesses. Its large industrial base highlights the potential for applying resource-sharing and waste-reduction strategies to various industries and company sizes, reinforcing the scalability of eco-industrial systems.

The park's integrated planning, provides a robust framework that addresses key aspects of mobility, economy, and environmental sustainability. This forward-thinking approach ensures coordinated development, aligning industrial activities with broader regional goals.

The closeness to residential areas emphasises Kanaalkant's status as a socially responsible model. By involving local communities in the redevelopment process, the park fosters social acceptance and strengthens support for its activities. This community-focused approach bridges the gap between industrial development and societal needs, making Kanaalkant a leader in balancing economic growth with social responsibility.

Sources: [34], [35], [36]

3.3.2 Kalundborg (Denmark)

Country:	Denmark
Geographical Scope:	Located in the city of Kalundborg, about 100 km west of Copenhagen
Status:	Operational since the 1970s; globally recognized as the first and most successful EIP
Size:	Network spans multiple industrial facilities in the Kalundborg region.
Number of members	16 public and private companies
Legal entity	<u>Managed by a general assembly and a board. The association comprises sixteen public and private companies in Kalundborg</u>
Actors:	Key actors: Asnæs Power Station, Novo Nordisk, Gyproc, and the Kalundborg municipality
Forms of Industrial Symbiosis:	<p><u>Energy:</u> Excess heat from the Asnæs Power Station is used for district heating and industrial processes.</p> <p><u>Materials:</u> By-products such as gypsum, fly ash, and sulfur are repurposed as inputs for other industries.</p> <p><u>Water:</u> Wastewater is reused as cooling water, reducing the need for fresh water.</p> <p><u>Waste Minimization:</u> Closed-loop systems turn waste streams into valuable resources.</p>
Relevance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decades of experience in resource-sharing and circular economy practices. • Efficient use of industrial waste heat for the city's district heating system. • Long-standing collaboration between industries and municipal authorities. • Stakeholders rely on each other, creating a resilient and self-sustaining network. • Emphasis on reducing environmental impact through waste and resource optimization. • Ongoing projects for energy efficiency, waste reduction, and new synergies.

The Kalundborg Eco-Industrial Park, located in Denmark, is celebrated globally as a pioneer and exemplar of sustainable industrial practices. Established in the 1970s, it was not originally designed as an EIP. Instead, it evolved organically through the innovative collaboration of local businesses, which identified opportunities to share resources, minimize waste, and optimize energy use. This unique approach has made Kalundborg a compelling business case for the eco-industrial model and a source of inspiration for similar initiatives worldwide.

Kalundborg is not strictly an urban EIP but is closely integrated with the nearby town. Surplus heat from the Asnæs Power Station is used for district heating, benefiting urban residents. The park also supports the local economy by creating jobs and reducing emissions, improving environmental quality for the town.

3.3.3 Relvão (Portugal)

Country:	Portugal
Geographical Scope:	Chamusca region
Status:	Operational since 2006
Size:	1,400 ha
Number of members	26 companies
Legal entity	The park itself does not operate as a single legal entity; instead, it functions through partnerships among various participants. Each entity within the park maintains its own legal status, contributing to the collective goal of sustainable industrial development.
Actors:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key actors: pulp and paper companies, agro industries, several chemical companies (mainly fertiliser producers), and waste treatment facilities, Portuguese Government, the Chamusca Municipality Government
Forms of Industrial Symbiosis:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Waste Material Exchange</u>: Manufacturers and Resource Recovery companies exchange waste materials such as plastics, batteries, and oils for recycling or further processing. • <u>Component Recovery and Redistribution</u>: Car dismantlers extract various vehicle components, sending metals for recycling and other materials (e.g., plastics, oils, batteries) to specialized companies within REIP. • <u>Inter-Company Waste and Service Exchange</u>: Resource Recovery companies exchange waste and services among themselves, fostering a circular approach to material utilization. • <u>Integration of Diverse Waste Streams</u>: Handling and processing of multiple waste types, including hazardous, municipal, urban, medical, and non-urban waste, ensuring comprehensive waste recovery.
Relevance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapting industrial ecology principles to local regulatory and economic contexts • Fostering sustainable and profitable waste recovery and material reuse. • Collaborations among diverse stakeholders facilitates symbiotic exchanges of materials and services • Scalable model for urban eco-industrial development.

The Relvão Eco-Industrial Park (REIP) / Chamusca Industrial Symbiosis demonstrates the potential of IE to adapt to regional regulatory and economic contexts, creating a sustainable and profitable framework for waste recovery and material reuse.

The municipality of Chamusca utilized waste management regulations and investments to establish the REIP, the first municipal EIP in Portugal. The initiative, termed Chamusca Industrial Symbiosis, centers on waste management and connects producers, farmers,

and local businesses. This collaboration involves various types of waste, including urban, medical, plastic, and battery waste, enabling exchanges of materials and services both within and beyond the park. Chamusca Industrial Symbiosis stands out due to its alignment with the Portuguese waste management system, which prioritizes recycling through resource recovery companies. Key facilities at REIP include national centers for hazardous waste recovery, municipal waste treatment, and facilities for specialized waste, such as plastics and batteries. These facilities successfully attracted recyclers, disassemblers, and waste sorters, such as car dismantlers who recycle vehicle components and direct materials like plastics, batteries, and oils to relevant companies.

One notable collaboration is between the battery processing facility and a civil explosives manufacturer. The processor recycles lead from batteries, which the manufacturer uses in its production, exemplifying a symbiotic business relationship. Additionally, the symbiosis fosters interactions among Resource Recovery companies, leading to efficient exchanges of waste materials and services.

The initiative achieved critical objectives, such as promoting sustainable bio-energy, expanding markets for secondary raw materials, increasing regional profitability, and reducing production costs. Success factors include diverse stakeholder involvement, equitable power dynamics, and strong participant commitment. These elements make Chamusca Industrial Symbiosis a transferable model for other regions, supported by standardized technologies and broadly applicable solutions. Efforts are ongoing to extend synergies to the surrounding Tagus Lezíria region.

Sources: [41], [42], [43], [44]

Figure 3-4: Relvão Eco-Industrial Park.
Source: [44].

3.3.4 Händelö (Sweden)

Country:	Sweden
Geographical Scope:	Händelö is located at a small island outside Norrköping (county of Östergötland), about 170 km southwest of Stockholm
Status:	Operational; city and industry collaborate for 20 years to utilize resource flows; an example of a leading industrial and urban symbiosis in bio-based and CE; industries successfully coexist with nature, high business and economic potential
Size:	600 ha island
Number of members/partner involved:	6 key actors: bio-ethanol company Lantmännen Agroethanol, energy company E.ON, the municipality, water and waste management Nodra, Port/Harbor, Linköping University
Legal entity:	Collaborative network
Forms of Industrial Symbiosis:	<p><u>Resource sharing and synergies, efficient energy utilization & circular by-product use</u></p> <p><u>Energy:</u> CHP is using residual products and waste as fuel (wood chips from the forest, waste from the city); electricity and district heating distribution of the city; residual steam from the CHP is delivered to the bio-ethanol company to manufacture ethanol and used for feed; bio-ethanol company returns condensate to energy company;</p> <p><u>Materials:</u> optimizing the use of raw materials; industries in the park share by-products and residual products f.e. farmers deliver grains and bakeries deliver cereals (old bakery, leftovers) to bio-ethanol company; leftover from ethanol production (residues) used to produce protein-rich animal feed; carbon dioxide is converted into carbonic acid and used in the food industry, residual products from the production of ethanol and feed are converted into biogas and fertiliser.</p> <p><u>Waste:</u> Waste for CHP (see above)</p>

Relevance:

- Within this eco-industrial park, they try to ensure that the resources of both industry and the city are efficiently interconnected within a collaborative system.
- Collaboration and synergies within the geographical proximity. Both in local (Norrköping city) and sub-local (Handelö area) level. Trust and communication are seen as key factors.
- innovation and expertise in sustainable renewable resources.
- Local actors depend on each other through their network. The presence of each actor increases the viability of another actor.
- Showcases industrial symbiosis in bio-based and circular economy, focus is mainly on by-product synergies and utility synergies.
- Continually spontaneously evolving projects; activities run in sup-project form (project on sustainable transport, project on potential for additional resources and energy efficiency, etc.) financed by the actors and the ERDF

On a small island in the city of Norrköping, in the region of Östergötland in East Sweden, the innovative Handelö Eco Industrial Park is located. The IS at Handelö Eco Industrial Park (HEIP) was motivated by the establishment of an ethanol plant near Norrköping. The plant chose its location strategically, near to sea access and the availability of competitive steam supply by the CHP plant. This forward-thinking industrial park is a best practice example of how green energy and IS can harmoniously integrate city and industry through bio-based and CE practices. By creating a synergetic network of actors, Handelö ensures that excess resources from both industry and urban life are utilized efficiently. With a strong commitment to renewable resource efficiency, the park showcases innovation and knowledge about green renewable resource efficiency. Collaboration among the companies at HEIP have been further improved when Region Östergötland and Cleantech Östergötland joined efforts. Their involvement enabled a three-year research initiative with project funding, driving further development of the park. Often companies lack resources for research and outreach, the support of academic actors and regional administration proved vital for advancing innovation and sustainability.

Figure 3-5: Handelö Eco-Industrial Park. Resource exchange between city and industry.

Source: [45].

- This **successful business case** demonstrates impressive achievements in resource efficiency and environmental sustainability, including the following key highlights: High resource efficiency
- Environmental benefits e.g. the bioethanol produced has a CO₂ emissions savings of >95% compared to production facilities based on fossil fuels
- Energy consumption/GHG emissions reductions: An annual 120,000 tCO₂
- Bio-based raw materials and by-products from the food industry become new material for bioethanol and feed
- Trust and communications are the most key factors in cooperation
- Green economies and clean technologies

Sources: [45], [46], [47], [48], [49], [50], [51]

3.3.5 Kwinana (Australia)

Country:	Australia
Geographical Scope:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Located in Kwinana, a city 40 km south of Perth in the Western Trade Coast, Western Australia • Largest and most sparsely populated state • The area has rich endowments of natural sources (e.g. gold, diamonds, iron ore, nickel, bauxite, oil, gas, coal, mineral sands)
Status:	Operational; established in the 1950s by the government; IS increased since the 1980s
Size:	12,000 ha
Number of members/partner involved:	No official number of companies involved but the number of employees is around 4,600 (direct) and 26,000 (indirect)
Legal entity:	Area comprises numerous independent operating companies. Kwinana Industries Council (integrated entity) is a peak industry association established in 1991, who represents the diverse range of industries in different priority areas of the Western Trade Coast.
Actors:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy process industries • Actors: alumina refinery, nickel refinery, titanium dioxide pigment plant, lime and cement kilns, oil refinery, iron plant, various chemical producers, utility operators (two power stations, two cogeneration plants, two air separation plants), grain handling, export terminal, port facilities, water/wastewater treatment plants
Forms of Industrial Symbiosis:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Diverse synergies</u>: by product and utility synergies • Approx. 150 existing interactions: Transfer of products, transfer of by-products, commercial cooperation • <u>Energy</u>: e.g. high-pressure steam network (CHP/oil refinery), oil refinery providing hydrogen for the three hydrogen fuel cell buses in Perth • <u>Materials</u>: e.g. by-products such as gypsum (chemical plant to alumina refinery), carbon dioxide (chemical plant alumina refinery residue area), by-products of a steel manufacturer for an iron plant • <u>Water</u>: Kwinana Water Reclamation Plant (water efficiency, reduce process water discharges), circular economy
Relevance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This industrial area reinforced the hypothesis that successful industrial symbiosis relies on fostering positive relationships across multiple dimensions, ultimately contributing to enhanced Circular Economy outcomes. • Showcase a broad based example of industrial symbiosis interactions (approx. 150)

- Key processing and manufacturing industries are highly diverse, with minimal competition among the companies .
- Industrial symbiosis projects developed with the facilitator Kwinana Industries Council
- Identification of industrial symbiosis possibilities by a research program
- Combination of skilled workforce, supportive industrial base and the governance framework.

The Kwinana Industrial Area was set up in the 1950s by the parliament to support the growth of resource-based processing industries. Nowadays KIA plays a very important role and is recognized as a cornerstone of the economy of Western Australia. The heavy and supporting industries provide direct employment to around 4,800 people and indirect employment to around 26,000 people. The companies generate an annual output valued at 15.77 billion \$ per year.

In 1991 the Kwinana Industries Council (KIC) was established by the core industries for the purpose to organize a collective air and water monitoring for the area, which is a sensitive marine environment. KIC fostered the interaction between companies, the government and the community and initiated a regional economic impact study (in the year 1990/2000), which documents the economic and social contribution of the KIA. The study included an analysis of the material and energy flows and the level of industrial integration and the complexity of IS. Between 1990 and 2000 the core process industries increased from 13 to 21 and the interactions increased up to 106. The awareness of IS potential increased within the industrial cluster. Currently, approximately 150 commercial exchanges are active among the industrial companies in the Kwinana Industrial Area.

Positive effects of the IS are economic, environmental and social benefits to companies and the neighbouring community.

There are a number of **unique features** of the Kwinana industrial area, which contributed to the successful IS. The key processing and manufacturing industries are highly diverse, with minimal competition among the companies. Although the area is relatively isolated from other industrial hubs in Western Australia, it benefits from close proximity to Perth and the gradual urban encroachment around the Kwinana Industrial Area. Furthermore, the region's rich natural resources significantly contribute to its industrial appeal. Additional features are the Kwinana Industries Council as facilitation and coordination centre and the economic impact studies.

Sources: [49], [52], [53], [54], [55], [56], [57]

Figure 3-6: Kwinana Industrial Area.
Source: [55].

3.3.6 Kawasaki (Japan)

Country:	Japan
Geographical Scope:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In Kawasaki city, Kanagawa Prefecture, Japan • Located between Tokyo and Yokohama, western shore of the Tokyo Bay • One of the most productive industrial cities in Japan
Status:	Operational; established by the city, recycling-oriented; ISO 14001 for the industrial complex
Size:	<p>Kawasaki city: 14,400 ha</p> <p>Kawasaki industrial zone 5,000 ha</p> <p>Kawasaki Eco-Town 2,800 ha</p> <p>Kawasaki Zero Emissions Industrial park 7,7 ha</p>
Number of members/partner involved:	<p>2,400 companies for Kawasaki industrial zone</p> <p>17 resident companies at the Kawasaki Zer-Emission Industrial Zone</p>
Actors:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy industry, energy intensive • Actors: second largest steel company in Japan, paper mill, cement company, food industry, metallurgical plants, oil refining, petrochemical and chemical industries, power stations, manufacturing of machinery and transport equipment, and other industries
Forms of Industrial Symbiosis:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Fusion of urban symbiosis and industrial symbiosis</u> • <u>Energy</u>: energy exchange (power) of steel company and Micro-Turbine to paper mill • <u>By-product exchange</u>: e.g. sludge, soot, blast furnace slag as raw material for cement production • <u>Water</u>: water recycling (use of processed water for production e.g. paper mill), highly treated water instead of industrial water • <u>Production</u>: cleaner production plans of companies • <u>Material/Waste</u>: reuse of waste from industrial, commercial, and municipal enterprises for use in industrial applications (recycling of plastic: as reducing agents, for concrete shuttering, for ammonia production; waste paper recycling plant; recycling of waste pet to virgin pet; scrap metal used as raw material for production, organic and construction waste used as raw material for cement production)

Relevance

- a fusion of urban and industrial symbiosis, which provides more opportunities for pollution and CO2 reduction
- demonstrates the successful transformation from a heavily industrialised city to a sustainable Eco-Industrial Park (EIP)
- partnership with the city administration, innovative strategies have been implemented and promoted to reduce environmental impact and promote sustainable development
- Shift from a heavily industrialized city to a sustainable Eco-Industrial Park (EIP).
- Close cooperation with city authorities to align industrial activities with urban sustainability goals.
- Extensive resource-sharing networks, emphasizing waste-to-resource strategies.
- Public-private collaboration fostering innovation and sustainable growth.
- Integration of smart technologies for energy efficiency and waste management.

Kawasaki experienced significant economic success throughout the 20th century, hosting a wide range of industrial sectors. However, by the early 1970s, air pollution had reached critical levels. Due to the close proximity of heavy industry to residential areas, the government took proactive measures by implementing an air pollution control agreement targeting the major industries in the region. In the 1990s, the government introduced policies aimed at revitalizing industries, enhancing environmental quality, and improving transport networks.

In 1997, the city developed a concept to become environmentally harmonious and became one of the first Eco-Towns. With government subsidies through the Eco-Town program, facilities were established to support sustainable development. A zero-emissions industrial complex was created for businesses utilizing advanced environmental technologies or practices, and subsidized recycling facilities were built.

These initiatives fostered further urban-industrial symbiosis. A comprehensive survey was conducted to identify input materials and by-products, resulting in 14 symbiotic and recycling projects that strengthened Kawasaki's commitment to sustainability.

Sources: [58], [59], [60], [61], [62]

Figure 3-7: Carbon Neutrality in Kawasaki.
Source: [58].

3.3.7 Ulsan (South Korea)

Country:	South Korea
Geographical Scope:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hyomun-dong and Yeonam-dong of Nam-gun, Dong-gu, and Buk-gu, Ulsan Metropolitan City located in the southeastern part of the country National Eco-industrial park Ulsan-Mipo EIP: six districts (Ulsan Petrochemical Industrial Complex, Yecheon District, Maeam District, Yongyeon District, Hyomun District, and Mipo District)
Status:	Operational, built in 1962 by the government, through national eco-industrial park initiative
Size:	4,565 ha
Number of members/partner involved:	853 companies with 104,944 employees
Actors:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> large companies, heavy industries actors: automobile, shipbuilding and petrochemical industries
Forms of Industrial Symbiosis:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>14 energy symbiosis networks on energy</u> <u>Energy</u>: 5 IS networks where the heat produced from waste incineration is used as energy source, 7 IS networks where process heat (chemical, petrochemical, smelting or other processes) is used as energy source, 1 IS network where the biogas is generated from treating organic waste liquids, such as livestock wastewater and food waste, through digestion, 1 IS network use of digestion gas
Relevance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One of the first and largest industrial zones in South Korea. A spontaneous transition of an industrial park into an Eco Industrial Park, incited by economic benefits and regulatory constraints. Korean EIP Program with a refined strategy: focus on larger-scale energy infrastructure development. Governments stakeholder engagement measures, city government provided support as part of their eco-city development plan - this created synergies.

The Ulsan Industrial Complex was developed as a conventional industrial estate with centralized energy provisions like electricity, steam, and water. The environmental regulations and the economic benefits of IS, resulted in more and more one-to-one IS. In 2004 the area was declared as Eco-Polis Ulsan and included a master plan with actions like the Ulsan Eco-Industrial Park Pilot project.

The objective of the Ulsan EIP project was to create opportunities to renovate the industrial complex and give it an upgrade by implementing IS. Key stakeholders of the project are Ulsan EIP centre, the government, various research and development centres and companies of the complex and Korea Industrial Complex Corporation.

To expand the IS in the industrial complex, the Ulsan EIP center developed a research and development into business framework and facilitates the symbiosis.

Industrial parks have presented a range of economic, environmental and social opportunities and challenges in Korea. Through the national Eco-Industrial Park initiative Ulsan city benefited with an energy and carbon emission reduction. Shah, I. H., Dong, L., & Park, H. S. (2020) conducted an eco-efficiency analysis on the eco-industrial development in the Ulsan area (not only Ulsan-Mipo EIP) between 2000 and 2015. Main findings of the analysis are that the eco-efficiency of industrial waste generation improved by 35 % and the energy use improved by 21,4 %. These improvements were driven by the reduction of waste and technical innovations.

Sources: [63], [64], [65], [66], [67], [68]

Figure 3-8: Overview of the Industrial Complex “Ulsan Mipo National Industrial Complex”.

Source: [63].

4 Key insights and recommendations

In the following, the results of the theoretical analysis and the data collection on EIPs are used to derive recommendations for ENERGIZE. The results are relevant for the project, as they provide the basis for possible designs for energy cooperation in urban and industrial areas in ENERGIZE's pilot regions.

4.1 Key insights based on theoretical outline

The review of the theoretical foundations and concepts in Section 2 shows that the need to improve the sustainability of industrial sites is and has been extensively researched in the literature and that concrete implementations of the concepts have taken place and are taking place. The developed concept of industrial symbiosis (IS) represents a theoretically effective approach to sustainability in the industrial sector. It is considered part of the knowledge field of industrial ecology, as it focuses on optimizing the material cycle and fulfills the principles of the circular economy. This means that by reusing, recycling and remanufacturing materials, resource efficiency is increased, waste and pollution are reduced and economic benefits are achieved.

Based on the concept of IS, EIPs are composed of several industrial enterprises located close to each other, taking advantage of their geographical proximity. Environmental protection and CO₂ reduction are considered as key factors in the development of cooperation between companies. The network of companies is based on the sharing of resources such as materials, energy, water, infrastructure and facilities. This approach minimizes resource consumption and waste. Cooperation also leads to cost savings and joint investments in sustainable energy infrastructures.

Within these EIPs, these advantages (investment, maintenance and infrastructure costs can be shared) also encourage cooperation to promote the increased use of renewable energy. In this way, industrial sites can become energy producers which are able to meet their own energy needs and supplying surplus energy to neighbouring residential areas. By focusing on the use of renewable energy and energy efficiency, CO₂ emissions are also reduced.

Different renewable energy technologies are used in urban EIPs. The use of these technologies depends on the specific circumstances of each EIP, including geographical location, resource availability and infrastructure conditions. In the context of urban-industrial symbiosis, waste heat is mainly used for heat supply, electricity and cooling, wastewater for heat supply, waste for heat supply and electricity and roof areas in combination with photovoltaic and solar thermal technologies for heat supply and electricity [4].

4.2 Key insights and derivations based on data collection

The insights gained from the analyses of industrial symbiosis initiatives are relevant to ENERGIZE, as they can serve as a basis for renewable energy cooperation between neighbouring companies and the targeted urban area in the pilot regions. By analyzing data from various eco-industrial parks (EIPs), key patterns and strategies can be identified that support renewable energy cooperations between industries and urban areas. These initiatives demonstrate how resource sharing, waste minimization, and energy efficiency measures can be successfully implemented to drive sustainability. The lessons learned from these examples offer practical guidance for ENERGIZE's pilot regions, helping to create scalable and adaptable cooperation models. As shown in Table 4-1, the data sets provide detailed and valuable information for the planning and implementation of ENERGIZE's initiatives.

Table 4-1: Key insights and derivations based on data collection.

Results from data collection	Derivations for ENERGIZE
<i>Country specific experiences</i>	The identified examples from different European and non-European countries provide a broad knowledge base for the energy cooperation targeted in ENERGIZE.
<i>Maturity of initiatives</i>	The fact that most of the parks are actively operating provides proven models for energy cooperation between industry and urban areas.
<i>Scalability</i>	The range of park sizes and forms of cooperation presented provides flexible options for cooperation in different urban and industrial contexts.
<i>Actors involved</i>	The involvement of companies, municipalities, utilities, SMEs, start-ups and research institutions shows that EIPs can foster diverse partnerships and interdisciplinarity.
<i>Spectrum of industries</i>	The industries represented - in particular the chemical industry, materials production and renewable energies - are also relevant for energy cooperation in ENERGIZE.
<i>Successful approaches</i>	Practices such as by-product exchange, recycling networks, and resource and infrastructure sharing provide practical guidance for implementing cooperation.
<i>Focus on renewable energy and energy efficiency</i>	Many initiatives emphasize the use of renewable energy sources and increasing energy efficiency, which directly support the ENERGIZE project objectives.
<i>Linking with urban areas</i>	Although the urban aspect is often not predominant, best practice examples (see Subsections 3.3 and 4.3) enable targeted concepts for involving urban stakeholders.

<i>Resource orientation</i>	Approaches such as “waste-to-resource” help to implement energy cooperation with a view to sustainability and efficiency.
<i>Supportive Policies</i>	Incentives, tax measures, and subsidies (e.g., from national governments and the EU) provide financial frameworks for energy cooperation and therefor support the formation of new initiatives.
<i>Integrated infrastructure</i>	Shared infrastructures such as heating systems, water treatment plants and waste recycling facilities strengthen the synergies of cooperation and promote the development of the parks in the initial stages.
<i>Environmental benefits</i>	Significant reductions in CO ₂ emissions and pollutants are observed, reinforcing the role of industrial symbiosis in achieving climate goals.

Source: Own compilation.

4.3 Key insights and recommendations based on best-practice examples review

The evaluation of selected best practice examples reveals critical findings and actionable recommendations for ENERGIZE. By analysing successful eco-industrial parks (EIPs) worldwide, strategies that have led to their success are identified and their applicability to ENERGIZE's objectives is examined. These recommendations provide valuable guidance for shaping ENERGIZE's initiatives, offering adaptable strategies for the pilot regions. These findings highlight resource efficiency, the integration of renewable energy and co-operation between different stakeholders.

Table 4-2: Key insights and recommendations based on selected best-practice examples.

Recommendation for ENERGIZE	Findings from selected best-practices
<i>Leveraging location advantages</i>	Strategic locations such as Kanaalkant (see Subsection 0) and Kalundborg (see Subsection 3.3.2) promote efficient use of resources and logistics.
<i>Create collaborative networks</i>	The success of many parks, such as Händelö (see Subsection 3.3.4), is based on cooperation between industry, companies, municipalities and research institutions.
<i>Integrate renewable energy</i>	Examples such as Händelö (see Subsection 3.3.4) and Kalundborg (see Subsection 3.3.2) show how surplus energy and bio-resources can be used in a sustainable way.
<i>Increasing resource efficiency</i>	The circular economy, such as in Kawasaki (see Subsection 3.3.6) and Relvão (see Subsection 3.3.3), demonstrates the value of material and energy cycles.

<i>Integrating social responsibility</i>	Kanaalkant (see Subsection 0) shows how involving local communities builds acceptance and support.
<i>Combining economic and environmental benefits</i>	Parks such as Ulsan (see Subsection 3.3.7) and Kwinana (see Subsection 3.3.5) benefit from innovative solutions to energy and material use.
<i>Flexibility in scaling</i>	The parks show that collaborations can be adapted to different sizes and industries.
<i>Incorporate regulatory support</i>	Relvão (see Subsection 3.3.3) and Kawasaki (see Subsection 3.3.6) highlight how government subsidies and policies facilitate implementation.
<i>Ensure long-term planning</i>	Successful initiatives develop master plans that combine sustainability and growth, as seen in Ulsan (see Subsection 3.3.7) and Händelö (see Subsection 3.3.4).
<i>Stakeholder education</i>	Kawasaki (see Subsection 3.3.6) and Kalundborg (see Subsection 3.3.2) emphasize stakeholder education to increase awareness of industrial symbiosis benefits and promote proactive participation.
<i>Promote Technological Innovation</i>	Parks like Kwinana (see Subsection 3.3.5) and Ulsan (see Subsection 3.3.7) invest in cutting-edge technologies for energy storage, waste processing, and resource optimization, providing ENERGIZE with a model for technology-driven solutions.
<i>Strengthen Urban-Industrial Integration</i>	Kalundborg (see Subsection 3.3.2) and Kanaalkant (see Subsection 0) show how integrating industrial parks with urban areas can benefit both parties through shared resources like district heating systems and improved urban infrastructure.
<i>Facilitation</i>	Various analysed EIPs (like e.g. Kwinana (see Subsection 3.3.5), Kawasaki (see Subsection 3.3.6), Ulsan (see Subsection 3.3.7)) show the importance of a facilitator. Facilitation enables productive collaboration and decision-making by fostering inclusivity, structure and communication.
<i>Industrial cluster</i>	Industrial clusters can be an opportunity to foster innovation, and competitiveness through collaboration and shared resources.

Source: Own compilation.

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